

EVOLUTION OF MEDIA LITERACY AND INFORMATION
CULTURE AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN SOCIETY

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Abstract: This article is about the evolution of media literacy and mass information culture and its importance in society. At the same time, its appearances are increasing. Today, the concepts of media education, media study, and media culture are used together with the concept of media literacy in receiving, sorting, analyzing, and evaluating media information.

Key words: media literacy, information, media education, technologies, media texts, information flow, mass information.

In recent years, the multifold acceleration of the flow of information, the increase of positive information as well as negative information has made it necessary to have media literacy. Traditionally, media literacy consisted of a person's ability to analyze literary works and create quality texts. Today, media literacy means knowing why and for what information is being transmitted. Who created this information for a media literate person and for what purpose? Is this message necessary for me? he should be able to ask the question and draw a correct conclusion, should be critical about it. These questions should be asked not only when you are watching TV with your family, listening to the radio in the car or watching the news on the Internet, but also when you are receiving and evaluating any information. Media literacy is important in understanding today's news environment.

Why is media literacy necessary?

- To understand the essence of the reforms implemented as a full-fledged, active citizen of our legal democratic society;
- Formation of skills for sorting out daily information transmitted and received through mass media;
- To avoid controlling the human mind through information and to make the right decision in any situation;
- To be able to analyze positive or negative changes of a person under the influence of visual images and to "read" invisible information given under visual messages;

- Analyzing the nature of textual communications given through mass media;

It is necessary to find answers to the questions of where, by whom and for what purposes the information is being transmitted, whose interests it reflects.

There are different opinions about the concept of media literacy, and according to the American International Encyclopedia of Society, it is noted that "media literacy" means being active and literate while feeling the responsibility as a citizen in society, being able to receive and create media texts, it means to be able to analyze and evaluate, to be able to understand the socio-cultural and political content of modern media.

The goal of media literacy is to understand the priorities and shortcomings of each media, to be able to sort out the information distributed by them and to form the skills to accept the necessary, while the main task is to limit it, realizing the manipulative power of any information consumed by people. It is also to help people understand the role of media and citizen journalism.

Currently, the concepts entering our language as a result of media analysis, i.e., media literacy, media education, media studies, etc., are related to each other, but scientists are trying to distinguish them from each other in essence. In our opinion, media literacy is an integral part of media education. At the same time, its appearances are increasing. Today, the concepts of media education, media study, and media culture are used together with the concept of media literacy in receiving, sorting, analyzing, and evaluating media information. What are their differences?

Media education:

- integrated, interdisciplinary study of media in the curriculum;
- to analyze the "media topic" within a specific discipline;
- critical approach to media through practical work and analysis;
- to study its form, technologies, methods of information transmission;
- to study media agencies, their social, political and cultural role;
- the student's work with media;
- research activities;
- studies the influence of the media on the audience through language and art.

Media studies in turn:

- theoretical study of media;
- comparative analysis of the media;
- its conceptual content;
- analysis of media text and its creation methodology;
- interdependence of mass communication, cinematography and cultural sciences;

- studies the interaction of world mass media.

Media literacy is the study of media, based on the following results of media education and aimed at:

- understanding the impact of media on individuals and society;
- understanding of mass communication process;
- being able to understand and analyze media texts;
- understanding the media context;
- creation of media texts and their analysis;
- sets the tasks of evaluating media texts and sorting them.

At the moment, it is necessary to include the basics of media education in the curriculum of every educational institution, to explain its basics to children in the form of interactive, various games during preschool education, to choose what is needed by the growing generation in the intense flow of information and to approach it critically. allows to evaluate without. This, in turn, is the basis for further strengthening of the citizenship position of young people in the future, for them to be able to objectively assess the events taking place in the world and make the right decisions.

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